

Using Wavelet Analysis to Study Structures and Properties of Structural Materials

M. L. Kheifetz

Institute of Applied Physics, National Academy of Sciences of Belarus, BELARUS

V. T. Senyut

Joint Institute of Mechanical Engineering of the National Academy of Sciences of Belarus, BELARUS

A. G. Kolmakov and A. A. Zverev

A. A. Baikov Institute of Metallurgy and Materials RAS, RUSSIA

B. M. Bazrov

A. A. Blagonravov Institute of Mechanical Engineering RAS, RUSSIA

It is proposed to use wavelet analysis to describe the structures of structural materials. The properties and parameters of wavelet analysis influencing the description of materials are determined. The application of wavelet analysis for the qualitative and quantitative description of the structures of structural materials is demonstrated, that makes it possible to assess the system characteristics of structures and to characterize the processes of self-organization in them.

The formation of friction surface structures for aluminum alloys with SiC and graphite additives in the scuffing mode is considered under comparable thermodynamic conditions. Using the example of aluminum alloys with additives, it is shown that the Mexican hat (MHAT) wavelet is more sensitive than the WAVE wavelet. The MHAT transformation is characterized mainly by a clear repetition of the profile with a narrowly pronounced maximum of the main contribution of the profile, while for the WAVE transformation a picture with a smooth maximum and a more smooth signal is obtained.

PACS numbers: 02.50.Uu, 02.70.-c, 28.41.Ak, 28.41.Kw, 28.41.Te, 28.52.Av

Keywords: thermodynamic conditions, wavelet analysis, structures of structural materials, aluminum alloys, friction surfaces

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10410180>

1. Introduction

At present, physicochemical analysis forms the basis of a systematic approach to the study of the structure formation of structural materials, technologies for their synthesis and destruction [1]. Wavelet analysis can be considered as a prospect for the development of a multilevel systems approach in materials science [2].

The wavelet functions of the basis allow to focus on certain local features of the analyzed processes that cannot be identified using the traditional Fourier and Laplace transforms [3, 4]. First of all, this concerns the fields of temperature,

pressure, various profiles, relief and other physical magnitude. The ability of wavelets to analyze non-stationary signals with a change in the component content in time or space is of fundamental importance.

2. Description of the structures of materials using wavelet analysis

One of the main and especially fruitful ideas of the wavelet representation of signals at various levels of decomposition is to divide the functions of approximation to the signal into two groups:

approximating, with a rather slow temporal dynamics of changes, and detailing, with local and fast dynamics of changes against the background smooth dynamics, followed by their fragmentation and detailing at other levels of signal decomposition [2]. This is possible in both the time and frequency domains of wavelet representation of signals.

Wavelet definition.

Any localized functions $\psi(t) \in L^2(R)$ can be used as generating wavelet and the family of functions $\{\psi_{ab}(t)\}$ constructed by dilatation and translation can be used as wavelet basis of the function space, if $\psi(t)$ satisfy certain conditions. Here parameter 'a' sets the width of the wavelet, parameter 'b' — localization, position on the time axis.

The before mentioned conditions is the following:

1. *localization*. The wavelet must be localized both in time (in space) and in frequency;
2. *regularity*. Fulfillment of the condition for zero torque and zero values of a certain number of subsequent moments;
3. *limitation*. Evaluating good boundedness and localization can be done using the expressions:

$$|\psi(t)| < 1/(1+|t|^n), \text{ or } |\psi(\omega)| < 1/(1+|k-\omega_0|^n),$$

where $|\psi(\omega)|$ is the average wavelet frequency. The number n should be as large as possible;

4. *self-similarity*. The self-similarity of the basis or the shape of the basis function must remain the same when shifting and scaling (stretching / shrinking).

Wavelets defined in this way allow representing any arbitrary function in the space $L^2(R)$ as a series (expansion in the basis $\psi_{ab}(t)$):

$$s(t) = \sum_{ab} C(a, b) \psi_{ab}(t),$$

where the coefficients $C(a, b)$ are the projections of the signal onto the basis of the space, which are determined by the scalar product:

$$C(a, b) = \langle s(t), \psi_{ab}(t) \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} s(t) \psi_{ab}(t) dt.$$

Conversion mapping.

The result of the wavelet transform of a one-dimensional number series (signal) is a two-dimensional array of values of the coefficients $C(a, b)$. The distribution of these values in space (a, b) gives the information about of the relative contribution of wavelet components of different scales in the signal at different times and is called the spectrum of wavelet transform coefficients, scale-time (frequency-time) spectrum, or simply wavelet spectrum.

The spectrum $C(a, b)$ of a one-dimensional signal is a surface in three-dimensional space. The most common way of displaying is a projection onto the (a, b) -plane with isolines (iso-levels), which makes it possible to trace changes in the coefficients at different scales over time, as well as to reveal the pattern of local extrema of these surfaces ("hills" and "valleys"), the so-called skeleton of the structure of the analyzed process [3, 4].

Wavelet analysis of the relief of friction surfaces.

When analyzing signals with even-type wavelets (MHAT), harmonic signals usually correspond to bright horizontal bands of wavelet spectra at the dominant wavelet frequencies, coinciding with the frequency of the harmonics of the signals. Disturbances in the smoothness of signals are recorded by vertical stripes. Peaks in signals are highlighted by maxima of wavelet coefficients. Wavelets of odd type (WAVE) react more sharply to jumps and rapid changes in signals, marking them with maxima or minima depending on the sign of the differentials. The more pronounced the features of the signals, the more they stand out on the spectrograms.

The wavelet spectrum of the original signal strongly depends on the parent wavelet and is a decomposition of the original signal in terms of the frequency and time scales of the parent

Table 1: Composition of samples and seizure parameters

No. Sam- ples	Fillers (wt%)	HB kg /mm ²	Parameters of transition to seizure		
			HB	n, rpm	t, min
1	—	62,4	70	600	11
2	5 % SiC	71,2	70	1500	1
3	2,5 % SiC + 1,25 % C	76,0	180	1500	1

Table 2: Calculated characteristics of α and β wavelet spectra.

Characteristics wavelet spectras	Sample no.		
	1	2	3
α WAVE	160,803	192,327	103,084
α MHAT	195,728	223,608	123,074
β WAVE	1,32975	2,29628	1,15961
β MHAT	1,95817	3,02989	2,11741

wavelet. Therefore, the choice of the mother wavelet is one of the most important tasks of the researcher, since with an improper choice of the mother wavelet, one may simply not see the desired features of the original signal.

In practice, the wavelet analysis is used, in particular, to study the profilograms of fracture surfaces of composite material samples in case of dry friction [2–4]. Two types of wavelets WAVE and MHAT are used as characteristic and well-studied representatives of odd and even wavelet bases, respectively, firstly, to compare their efficiency in reflecting profile features in isolines and, secondly, to compare their capabilities for comparing profiles related to various materials.

3. Wavelet analysis of the structures of the surface layer of aluminum alloy

Wavelet analysis was used to quantitatively describe the structures of the friction surface [2–4]. Samples of cast composite materials (CM) based on the aluminum alloy (in wt%: Al - base, 10...12 Si, 0.02 Cu, 0.35 Fe, 0.06 Zn, 0.08 Ti, 0.08 Ca), in which various fillers are introduced such as high-modulus ceramic SiC particles (average diameter \varnothing 30 μ m) and graphite particles

($\varnothing < 400 \mu$ m) as a dry lubricant [5].

Dry friction tests were carried out on a friction test equipment according to the axial loading scheme of the bushings ($d_d = 28$ mm, $d_w = 20$ mm, $h = 16$ mm) at constant loads from 70 to 180 N and sliding speeds, variable in the range from 0.2 to 1.85 m/s (300...1500 rpm). The counterbodies were made of chrome steel (HRC ≥ 45) [5]. The dry friction behavior of specimens made of CM and aluminum alloy (Al alloy) used as matrix was evaluated by the load and sliding speed, leading to seizure and galling. The samples were brought to a seizure state (Table 1).

The structures of the friction surfaces were studied using a LEO 430i scanning electron microscope (Fig. 1).

For the initial information on the structures of the relief of the friction surface, profilograms with the scale of 10 mm corresponding to 1 μ m were used (Fig. 2).

To construct the surface of the wavelet spectrum, the points of the profile were taken along the scale grid, i.e. with a step of 0.1 μ m [2, 6, 7]. The Wolfram Mathematica software from Wolfram Research was used to draw surfaces and isolines.

From the obtained vector of profile values, by means of the dot product, the spectral coeffi-

FIG. 1: Scuffing relief of samples with numbers: 2 – 5% SiC (a); 3 – 2.5 % SiC + 1.25% C (b).

FIG. 2: Profiles of the analyzed friction surfaces for samples with numbers 1 (a), 2 (b), 3 (c).

cients were calculated over the grid of profilogram values. The step of the two-dimensional matrix of coefficients was taken with a similar step, which is natural in the case of analyzing a profile, rather than a signal in time.

The spectrum of the model “ideal” profile

was also calculated for comparison and substantiation of the results. In order to obtain a complete picture for wavelet analysis, in this case, both types of wavelets WAVE and MHAT were used.

The resulting wavelet spectra are shown in

FIG. 3: (Color online) Surfaces of wavelet spectra for profilograms: from the 1st sample — WAVE (a) and MHAT (b); from the 2nd sample — WAVE (c) and MHAT (d); from the 3rd sample — WAVE (e) and MHAT (f).

Fig. 3; the corresponding level pictures are shown in Fig. 4.

The obtained characteristics of the wavelet analysis α and β are shown in Table 2; for a visual representation of the nature of the change

in wavelet characteristics, diagrams “ $\alpha - \beta$ ” are constructed (Fig. 5).

The analysis of the patterns of level lines (isolines) of various wavelets on small scales of coordinates showed that the results of both trans-

FIG. 4: Line patterns of wavelet spectra levels for profilograms: from the 1st sample — WAVE (a) and MHAT (b); from the 2nd sample — WAVE (c) and MHAT (d); from the 3rd sample — WAVE (e) and MHAT (f).

FIG. 5: “ $\alpha - \beta$ ” diagrams of wavelet spectra WAVE (a) and MHAT (b).

formations practically coincide, but is changed for the scales exceeded main contribution of profilogram.

So, for the MHAT transformation as a whole, a very clear repetition of the profile with a narrowly expressed maximum of the main contribution of the profile is characteristic; for the WAVE transformation, a picture with a smooth maximum and also a more smooth signal is obtained.

Based on the obtained isolines, we can conclude that if you need a fine study of the profile, the MHAT transformation is more suitable, if, on the contrary, you need to find out the general nature of the profile, not paying attention to small details, then you should use the WAVE transformation.

The analysis of the location of the points of values on the “ $\alpha - \beta$ ” diagram for the studied samples (see Fig. 5) showed that the form of dependence on the use of even or odd wavelets does not change much, but depends to a greater extent on the form of the parent wavelet. It turned out

that the MHAT wavelet is more sensitive than the WAVE wavelet. In particular, the diagram for the MHAT wavelet clearly shows the “dip” β for the 1st sample, which is not revealed by the WAVE wavelet.

4. Conclusion

It is proposed to use wavelet analysis to describe the structures of materials. The properties and parameters of wavelet analysis influencing the description of materials are determined. It is shown that the use of a wavelet spectrum obtained as a result of a discrete or continuous wavelet transform of a time series allows one to obtain information about the time evolution of the relative contribution of substructures of various scales.

The formation of friction surface structures for aluminum alloys with SiC and graphite additives in the scuffing mode is considered under comparable thermodynamic conditions. Using the example of aluminum alloys with additives, it is shown that the MHAT wavelet is more sensitive than the WAVE wavelet.

Thus, the use of a systematic approach in materials science allows for a significant development of traditional methods and their effective application for objects with a complex multiscale structure, including nanostructured materials.

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